

Synthesis of some Nitro-substituted 1,3,4-Oxadiazoles, 1,3,4-Thiadiazoles and 1,2,4-Triazoles as Antiamebic Agents

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Some 2-(β -arylethyl)-5-phenylamino-1,3,4-oxadiazoles, 2-(β -arylethyl)-5-phenylamino-1,3,4-thiadiazoles and 3-(β -arylethyl)-4-phenyl-5-mercapto-1,2,4-triazoles have been synthesised through thiosemicarbazides. All these compounds have been tested *in vitro* for their amoebicidal activity against *B. histolytica*.

SOME heterocyclic compounds such as oxadiazoles, thiadiazoles and triazoles have been widely reported to possess various biological activities¹. Presence of nitro moiety in these heterocyclic compounds has been regarded as being essential for the enhancement of antiamebic and antibacterial activities. Our continued interest in the evaluation of biological activities has prompted us to synthesise some nitro-substituted oxadiazoles, thiadiazoles and triazoles.

Aryl esters were prepared and reacted with hydrazine hydrate in ethanol to give arylacetylhydrazines. These hydrazines were treated with phenylisothiocyanate to form the respective thiosemicarbazides. Reaction of the thiosemicarbazides with mercuric oxide in methanol resulted in the formation of 1,3,4-substituted-oxadiazoles². The thiosemicarbazides were also cyclised into 1,3,4-substituted-thiadiazoles in presence of concentrated H_2SO_4 . Triazoles (1,2,4-substituted) have been obtained by refluxing the thiosemicarbazides with sodium hydroxide solution. The structures of the compounds were established on the basis of ir and pmr spectral data.

Experimental

Ir spectra (KBr) were recorded on a Pye-Unicham SP 2000 spectrophotometer, and pmr spectra ($CDCl_3$) on a Varian T-60 (60 MHz) instrument with tetramethylsilane as internal standard.

Substituted-benzylacetylhydrazines were prepared by the reported method³. The substituted-hydrazines (0.1 mol) suspended in ethanol were treated with phenyl isothiocyanate (0.12 mol) and refluxed over a water-bath for 2–3 h. The thiosemicarbazides (1) obtained on cooling the reaction mixture were filtered off and washed with ethanol, dried and recrystallised from hot methanol.

2-(β -Arylethyl)-5-phenylamino-1,3,4-oxadiazoles (2): 1-(β -Aryl)propionylthiosemicarbazide (1; 0.10 mol) was dissolved in methanol and mercuric oxide (0.15 mol) was added. The reaction mixture was refluxed for 2 h and filtered hot. The filtrate was concentrated and the resulting solid (2a) was recrystallised from aqueous ethanol, 3 320–3 290 (NH), 1 610–1 600 (conjugated cyclic C=N) and 3 060–3 010 cm^{-1} (aromatic CH): 2a (69.5%), m.p. 189°; δ 2.90 (4H, s, CH_2CH_2), 6.60 (5H, s, ArH), 7.05 (2H, s, ArH) and 6.75 (5H, s, ArH); 2b (76.5%), m.p. 211°; δ 3.0 (4H, s, CH_2CH_2), 7.50 (5H, s, ArH) and 6.10 (2H, s, OCH_2O); 2c (71.3%) m.p. 119°; δ 3.05 (4H, s, CH_2CH_2), 6.5 (H, s, furan C_2-H), 7.30 (H, s, furan C_2-H) and 7.15 (5H, s, ArH).

2-(β -Arylethyl)-5-phenylamino-1,3,4-thiadiazoles (3): 1-(β -Aryl)propionylthiosemicarbazide (1; 0.10 mol) was dissolved with cooling in concentrated H_2SO_4 (10 ml). The solution was kept at room temperature for 2 h with stirring from time to time and then poured over crushed ice. It was stirred well and allowed to stand for 1.5 h. The residue 3a was filtered, washed with water and recrystallised from ethanol, 3 320–3 270 (NH stretch), 1 620–1 570 (conjugated cyclic C=N) and 3 030–2 970 cm^{-1} (aromatic CH stretch): 3a (73.0%), m.p. 167°; δ 3.0 (4H, s, CH_2CH_2), 6.60 (2H, s, ArH), 7.05 (2H, s, ArH) and 6.90 (5H, s, ArH); 3b (75.0%) m.p. 152°; δ 2.85 (4H, s, CH_2CH_2), 6.00 (2H, s, OCH_2O)

and 7.35 (5H, s, ArH) ; **3c** (79.0%), m.p. 141° ; δ 2.95 (4H, s, CH_2CH_2), 6.6 (H, s, furan $\text{C}_3\text{-H}$), 7.4 (H, s, furan $\text{C}_4\text{-H}$) and 7.25 (5H, s, ArH).

3-(β -Arylethyl)-4-phenyl-5-mercapto-1,2,4-triazoles (4) : Equimolecular quantities of β -arylpropionylhydrazine (0.01 mol) and phenyl isothiocyanate (0.01 mol) were refluxed in 10% sodium hydroxide solution (20 ml) for 4–5 h, cooled and filtered. The clear filtrate was acidified with HCl and the precipitated triazole (**4a**) was filtered off, washed and recrystallised from ethanol, 1 630–1 570 (conjugate cyclic C=N), 2 530–2 500 (SH) and 3 000–2 970 (aromatic CH stretch) : **4a** (67.7%), m.p. 116° ; δ 2.95 (4H, s, CH_2CH_2), 6.70 (2H, s, ArH), 7.20 (2H, s, ArH) and 7.0 (5H, s, ArH) ; **4b** (62.5%), m.p. 123° ; δ 2.95 (4H, s, CH_2CH_2), 6.10 (2H, s, OCH_2O), 7.25 (5H, s, ArH) ; **4c** (78.2%), m.p. 109° ; δ 3.0 (4H, s, CH_2CH_2), 6.7 (H, s, furan $\text{C}_3\text{-H}$), 7.30 (H, s, furan $\text{C}_4\text{-H}$) and 7.25 (5H, s, ArH).

Pharmacological evaluation : The compounds were tested *in vitro* against axenically grown *E. histo-*

lytica at pH 7.2–7.4. The amebicidal end-point of compounds **1**, **3** and **4** from **a** to **c** were found to be 500, 125, 125 ; 500, 250, 250 ; N.A., 500, 250 $\mu\text{g ml}^{-1}$ respectively. The compounds exhibited very mild to moderate amebicidal activity as compared with the standard drug nitromidazole whose amebicidal end-point being 7.75 $\mu\text{g ml}^{-1}$.

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